

1+MG video promotion guidelines

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Introduction

These guidelines are designed to support the 1+Million Genomes initiative at national level to effectively promote the initiative through video content on digital channels. The aim is to help increase the visibility and impact of the 1+MG video content among diverse audiences – spanning the general public, healthcare professionals, researchers, and funders as well as policymakers. These guidelines are intended to help those involved in both international and national engagement and dissemination efforts.

Actionable Steps

Translate Core Content

Adapt the central video assets by translating subtitles and contextualising messaging for national audiences (ensuring country relevance, clarity, and accessibility across languages and health systems).

Create a Focused Awareness Campaign with Audience-Specific Outreach and Social Media Posts

Use the PESO framework to develop tailored communications and posts for platforms like LinkedIn (for professionals), Facebook and Instagram (for the public), and X (for wider visibility), with video and accompanying text targeted to each audience segment.

Develop a Dedicated Landing Page for 1+MG Video Content

Create specific landing pages on the GDI project website and also national-level websites that feature the videos (including translations), with key messages for different audiences, clear calls to action, and (if possible) downloadable resources. At a national level, this page could serve as a trusted hub for national outreach, aligned with the broader international 1+MG brand and communication goals.

Example of embedding 1+MG video on the national website:

- Portugal: embedded the video in news release ([link](#))
- Czech Republic: a dedicated 1+MG website with a separate page to host videos ([link](#))

Track and Report Engagement Metrics

Monitor performance across social, website, and newsletter platforms by tracking views, clicks, shares etc. Submit and circulate regular reports using a shared template to enable coordinated evaluation and improvement across all countries.

Key Messaging

The core narrative of the 1+Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative is built around its mission to create a secure, federated, and ethically governed framework that enables cross-border access to genomic and clinical data across Europe. This effort is designed to advance personalised healthcare, accelerate scientific research, and inform better health policy by harmonising data standards, ensuring quality, and fostering collaboration among EU member states. At its heart, 1+MG aims to make genomics a key part of healthcare delivery in a way that respects individual rights and national differences.

To communicate this effectively, all messaging should offer a clear and unified description of the initiative's purpose, goals, and broader societal impact. However, specific key points should be adapted to different audiences—citizens, healthcare professionals, funders, policymakers, and researchers—taking into account cultural context and language. While the tone and style may vary slightly by country, all communications should remain open, accessible, trustworthy, and grounded in evidence, especially when engaging the general public.

Target Audiences

The 1+Million Genomes initiative targets four primary audiences: EU citizens and patients, healthcare professionals, funders and policymakers, and life science researchers. Citizens and patients currently have low awareness of the initiative and are particularly concerned about the privacy, security, and control of their personal health data. They are motivated by the promise of improved diagnosis, treatment, and prevention but require clear, trustworthy information to build confidence. Social media platforms (such as Instagram, Facebook and X) as well as YouTube and the project website are key channels for reaching this group, with video content serving as an effective tool for making complex genomic topics accessible and relatable.

Healthcare professionals, likewise, currently have limited awareness of the 1+MG initiative but show strong interest in how patient data can improve outcomes and healthcare delivery. Their primary concerns include the time and resource demands associated with data collection and consent processes, as well as the need for authoritative guidance they can relay to their patients. Communication to them should be concise, evidence-based, and delivered through trusted sources.

Similarly, funders and policymakers are looking for high-quality data that can guide strategic decisions and improve healthcare systems, and they value visibility of measurable outcomes and alignment with national or EU priorities. They are best reached through policy briefs, white papers, stakeholder events, and digital platforms like LinkedIn and X as well as institutional channels.

Life science researchers, while motivated by the potential of genomic data to advance personalised medicine and public health, remain cautious about inconsistent data quality, unclear governance,

and access barriers. They rely on academic journals, research platforms, and professional platforms like ResearchGate and LinkedIn to stay informed.

All four audience groups have unique sensitivities that are best addressed through transparent and focussed communication. Tailoring messages to their values, expectations, and preferred platforms is essential in building trust, ensuring engagement, and supporting the long-term success of the 1+MG initiative.

Local Adaptation Guidelines

When adapting 1+Million Genomes (1+MG) content and assets for local use, national communications team members should adapt the accompanying messaging to reflect the cultural context, language preferences, and healthcare landscape of their country.

While maintaining alignment with the core narrative and objectives of the initiative, communications should be adjusted to resonate with local audiences – whether that means text in social media posts using simpler language for the general public, incorporating regionally relevant examples, or emphasising national benefits. Translating subtitles and captions into local languages is essential, but care should be taken to preserve meaning and tone rather than relying solely on literal translation. Key messages should also address country-specific concerns, such as national data governance frameworks or health system priorities, to build relevance and trust.

In terms of style and content, visual assets such as video clips, infographics, and social media templates should be customised with country-appropriate imagery, voices, or spokespeople where possible. National groups are encouraged to produce supplementary materials, such as locally focused blog posts, explainers, or interviews, to contextualise the initiative within national conversations on genomics, health equity, and innovation. All adapted content should remain consistent with the initiative's overall tone (open, evidence-informed, and trustworthy) while allowing for flexibility in how stories are told. It's also important to ensure that translated and localised content is accessible via the platforms most used by local audiences and aligns with national communication norms, whether that means Facebook posts or organisational LinkedIn posts.

TRANSLATION GUIDELINES

When translating content for the 1+MG initiative, the goal is not only to convert language but to preserve meaning, tone, and intent across diverse cultural contexts. Translations should be handled by native speakers or professional translators with subject-matter familiarity in genomics and health communication to ensure accuracy/clarity. It's essential that medical and technical terms are correctly interpreted and that commonly misunderstood concepts (like data privacy or consent) are translated with care to avoid ambiguity. Subtitles, video captions, and social media copy should be concise and culturally appropriate, avoiding idioms or metaphors that may not translate well or could cause confusion.

Translated materials should also be reviewed by a second group of local stakeholders (communications staff, healthcare professionals, or patient representatives) to validate clarity and appropriateness before distribution. Where necessary, offer subtitles in multiple regional languages to improve inclusivity, and ensure that translation formatting adheres to best practices (i.e. subtitle lines are not overly long). It's also important to maintain visual consistency across languages – ensuring that fonts, spacing, and layout remain similarly branded for burnt-in subtitles, for example. For websites or platforms such as YouTube with multilingual functionality, translated content should be easy to toggle on and off (and visibly linked from the main English-language assets in the case of multilingual websites).

The document with timecodes for translation and subtitling can be found on the [GDI Google drive](#). Each country can create a folder to host their translation. Once the translation is complete, please contact ELIXIR Communications Officer, Zippy Tseng (yun-yun.tseng@elixir-europe.org) to include the translation on YouTube CC subtitle.

Channel Strategy

Choosing the right digital channel is essential to ensure your message reaches the intended audience in a format they trust, understand, and engage with. Different platforms cater to different behaviors and expectations, so aligning your content with where and how your audience consumes information increases both reach and impact. This is true both at a national and international level.

LINKEDIN

Primary Audience:

Healthcare professionals, policymakers, funders, researchers, institutional partners.

Best Content Types:

Natively uploaded expert videos (2–3 minutes)

Best Time to Post:

Tuesday to Thursday, 10:00–12:00 CET

Posting Frequency:

2–3 times per week

Additional Tips:

- Post both from central “company” page(s) and individual/interviewee pages
- Tag partner institutions and relevant people/stakeholders for amplification
- Use hashtags like #Genomics, #EUHealth, #1MillionGenomes
- Include clear calls to action (e.g., “Watch the video”)

X

Primary Audience:

General public, health advocates, journalists, researchers, digital policy followers.

Best Content Types:

- Short posts with 1–2 key messages (max 280 characters)
- Threads explaining complex ideas (e.g., benefits of genomic sharing)
- Short 30 second “teaser” video clip(s)

Best Time to Post:

Weekdays between 09:00–11:00 or 17:00–18:30 CET

Posting Frequency:

3–5 times per week

Additional Tips:

- Use hashtags for greater reach (#PersonalisedMedicine, #HealthData, #GenomicsEU)
- Tie in with EU health or science awareness days for visibility

FACEBOOK

Primary Audience

EU citizens and patients, patient advocacy groups, caregivers, older adults.

Best Content Types:

Video explainers with subtitles

Best Time to Post:

Weekdays at 12:00–14:00 or evenings 18:00–20:00 CET

Posting Frequency:

2–3 times per week

Additional Tips:

- Create or join health-related Facebook groups for organic outreach
- Keep copy simple, warm and reassuring

INSTAGRAM

Primary Audience:

Younger citizens, digitally engaged patients, public health communicators.

Best Content Types:

- Short video reels (30–60 seconds) with engaging captions (square and vertical)
- Instagram Stories

Best Time to Post:

Weekdays 11:00–13:00 or 17:00–19:00 CET

Posting Frequency:

3–4 times per week (mix of feed + Stories)

Additional Tips:

- Use alt-text and accessible captions for inclusivity
- Avoid dense text – the videos should communicate the core message
- Collaborate with medical/healthcare influencers or advocacy groups for reach

EMAIL NEWSLETTERS

Primary Audience:

Existing supporters, researchers, policymakers, National Mirror Groups

Best Content Types:

- Monthly/quarterly project update emails with links to videos
- Embedded video thumbnails or GIFs to increase engagement and click through rate

Best Time to Send:

Tuesday or Thursday mornings between 08:00–10:00 CET

Sending Frequency:

Once per month/quarter (with optional mid-month bulletins for time sensitive announcements)

Additional Tips:

- Include clear calls to action ("Watch now," "Share with your network")
- Segment lists by audience type when possible (researchers vs. citizens)
- Track open rates and click-throughs to optimise future content

PESO Framework Application

In the context of the 1+MG initiative, the PESO model offers a comprehensive framework for amplifying digital communications and running a focussed awareness campaign.

PESO stands for Paid, Earned, Shared, and Owned media. Paid media involves targeted promotions such as paid LinkedIn posts or Google search ads to increase video views and awareness among citizens, healthcare professionals, and policymakers. Earned media focuses on building credibility through coverage in trusted media outlets, expert interviews, and third-party shares, helping establish the initiative's authority. Shared media takes advantage of organic sharing on social platforms like X, Facebook, and LinkedIn to engage audiences through community interaction, resharing, and two-way dialogue. Owned media includes ELIXIR's YouTube channel, newsletters, and dedicated GDI project website which can serve as the central hub for informative and accessible content tailored to each audience segment. Together, these channels reinforce each other to build awareness, trust, and sustained engagement across Europe.

National teams can effectively apply the PESO model by adapting national level communications activities within each category to their local context. Under Paid media, they can run geotargeted and localised LinkedIn or Facebook ad campaigns to promote the 1+MG videos to relevant national audiences such as healthcare professionals or patient communities. For Earned media, teams can issue press releases or connect with similar initiatives/organisations to share stories or expert opinion pieces on other social media accounts/websites/newsletters. In the Shared media space, they should actively post on their organisational and individual X, Facebook, and LinkedIn accounts, encouraging local partners, influencers, and professional networks to reshare content and join the conversation. Finally, for Owned media, National Mirror Group websites, newsletters, and YouTube channels can host or embed the 1+MG videos with translated subtitles and publish locally relevant explainer articles to sustain long-term public engagement and reinforce trust.

Website Integration

A strong website landing page is essential for converting social media interest into meaningful engagement, providing a clear and accessible destination where users can explore more about the initiative. It serves as an entry point to a trusted hub for information, videos, and calls to action, helping audiences deepen their understanding and take the next step – from watching a video to sharing it.

AUDIENCE-CENTRIC DESIGN

The landing page should be structured with the user in mind, offering clear navigation paths for each of the core audiences: EU citizens and patients, healthcare professionals, funders and policymakers, and life science researchers. Use simple, non-technical language for public-facing sections / web copy while providing links to more detailed resources for expert users such as the [1+MG Framework](#).

Visual tabs or buttons that allow users to self-select their audience type can help streamline their experience and ensure they find the most relevant content quickly.

VIDEO-CENTERED LAYOUT

As the communications campaign is centred on video content, the main overview video should be positioned prominently at the top of the page (embedded from YouTube) and accompanied by a short text description. Below, a gallery of audience-specific videos should be displayed with clear labels and summaries – including the longer form interview edits. Make sure to include subtitle options in multiple languages to increase accessibility and reach across different national contexts.

CLEAR CALLS TO ACTION (CTAs)

Effective CTAs should guide users toward deeper engagement, with clear buttons such as “Watch Now” or “Learn More”. These should be placed near each video, at the top and bottom of the page, and repeated where relevant. CTAs should be tailored by audience where possible, such as “Watch Video for Healthcare Professionals.”

TRUST-BUILDING ELEMENTS

To help strengthen credibility, the landing page should include logos of funding EU bodies, project partners, and participating institutions. Featuring short text quotes or testimonials from researchers, clinicians, or patient advocates can help build emotional trust. Consider offering downloadable PDFs like fact sheets or executive summaries to provide clear, verified information that users can share or reference offline.

WEBSITE OPTIMISATION

The landing page must be mobile-responsive and load quickly to ensure users stay engaged. Integrate social sharing buttons with pre-populated text to encourage users to share content easily on their preferred platforms. Use analytics tools to monitor visitor behavior, track video views, and identify any drop-off points, allowing for data-driven content updates over time.

ACCESSIBILITY AND INCLUSIVITY

Ensure the landing page meets accessibility standards by including alt-text for all images, screen reader compatibility, and proper colour contrast ratios for text. Navigation should be fully keyboard-accessible. Provide a language selection menu and translated versions of content such as subtitles to ensure equitable access.

Measurement and Reporting

Measuring and reporting are essential in communication campaigns to assess what's working, identify areas for improvement, and ensure resources are used effectively. Regular analysis of key metrics such as engagement, reach, and video views enables data-driven decisions that enhance impact and accountability.

Tracking key metrics across social media, newsletters, and websites is crucial for understanding audience engagement and improving communication effectiveness. On social media, metrics such as views, impressions, engagement rate, click-through rate, and follower growth help gauge how well content is resonating and being shared. For email newsletters, open rates indicate subject line effectiveness and audience interest, while click through rates (CTRs) reveal how compelling the content is and whether it drives further action. On websites, page views, bounce rate, time on page, and video watch time show how users are interacting with the content and where they may lose interest. Monitoring these metrics allows teams to refine messaging, adjust formats, and prioritise the most effective channels to reach and engage their audiences.

Please see the accompanying quarterly reporting template spreadsheet for ease of reporting and tracking.